

AGROSUS

AGROecological strategies for
SUStainable weed management
in key European crops

MULTI-ACTOR APPROACH PROJECT BASED ON

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Biogeographical
regions

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Short term
farming systems

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Crops

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Regional Stakeholders'
Communities

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Crop-linked
Groups

Universidade de Vigo

Funded by
the European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No GA 101084084.

